

PODCAST TECHNOLOGY - THE TECHNOLOGY OF THE FUTURE

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To achieve success in the modern world, a person needs to master a foreign language, which is one of the main conditions of modernity. Therefore, it is not surprising that recently more and more attention has been paid to learning English. However, for its successful mastering, only lessons at the university are not enough. Extracurricular, independent activity of students is essential. Moreover, taking into account the rapid progress and development of innovative technologies, the organisation of independent learning of a foreign language, in particular English becomes easier and more interesting.

Podcast technology is one of the most popular means of independent foreign language learning abroad, but a little-known and little-researched phenomenon in domestic science.

Modern Internet technologies, including the social service of podcasting are of interest to many scientists and are a key subject of research E. Polat, E. Titova, L. Raitskaya, P. Sysoev, M. Evstigneev, A. Filatova, N. Sushkova, T. Pavelieva, G. Danya, N. Hockley, I. Volvacheva, B. Salin, A. Avramenko, Sh. Robinson, A. Solomatina and others.

Actually the word ‘podcast’ (podcast) is a combination of the words ‘iPod’ (MP3 player of Apple) and ‘broadcast’ (widespread large-format broadcasting) [2]. And the term ‘podcasting’ means a way to distribute audio or video information on the Internet.

P. Constentine gives the following definition of the term ‘podcast’: ‘Podcast is a term used to refer to a digital recording of a radio programme or other type of file. Podcasts are published on the Internet as MP3 files. Interested listeners are able to download these files to a personal computer, or MP3 player of any type. These files can be listened to anytime and anywhere. Podcasts can be listened to repeatedly. They can be either short (2 to 3 minutes) or long (up to 1 hour). Learners can subscribe to the RRS - newsletter’ [2]. Podcasts of certain topics and certain sections appear on the Internet regularly: every day, once a week, per month, etc.

Since 2005, the process of using and creating podcasts as a computer-independent, fast and profitable technology has reached a point of highest popularity abroad. It was in this year that The New Oxford American Dictionary named the term ‘podcast’ as ‘Word of the Year’ [3].

Today there is a huge number of podcasts on the Internet, which are different in terms of topics (everyone can subscribe to those podcasts that interest him/her: politics, culture, sports, news, etc.), genre (there are joke podcasts, song podcasts, story podcasts, etc.), purpose (for example, using a podcast to improve certain skills), etc.

Working with podcasts has many positive aspects. By working with podcasts you can learn to overcome language barriers and not be afraid to make mistakes. Podcasts can be of interest to learners because they contain relevant material on all areas of knowledge. They can be supplemented with country-specific photos or videos. Podcasts with captions or accompanying text are very useful in understanding learning material [2].

Educational podcasts devoted to learning a foreign language allow solving certain tasks, including the formation and improvement of listening and pronunciation skills, expansion and enrichment of vocabulary, formation and improvement of grammatical skills, development of oral and written skills [2].

The benefits of using podcasts include:

1. the opportunity to develop the skill of learning autonomy;
2. the opportunity to individualise the learning process;
3. the possibility of expanding the boundaries of the learning environment;
4. the possibility of organising intercultural communication;
5. the possibility of forming information competence;
6. the possibility of using a huge amount of educational material for teaching different types of speech activity;
7. reduction of psychological difficulties;
8. providing free access to authentic materials for independent learning of a foreign language;
9. ease of use [3].

Thus, podcasts are a multifunctional learning tool that contributes to the effectiveness of learning a foreign language, particularly English, motivates to further learning, makes the process of independent learning interesting and effective.

The main goal of learning a foreign language is to acquire communicative competence, i.e. the ability to communicate in a foreign language in the real world. Therefore, authentic materials, among which we can name podcast - technologies, play a very important role. Podcast, being one of the most popular ways to learn a language, is very widespread on the Internet. Many websites offer foreign language learners to use their service to improve their skills through podcasts, but they all have their advantages and disadvantages:

Podcast resources

<http://www.podcastsinenglish.com/index.shtml>

- The material is structured by levels of English language proficiency; audio and video podcasts are available; the possibility to use lesson plans for podcasts.

- Podcasts are downloaded for free, but assignments are paid.

<http://www.breakingnewsenglish.com/>

- Podcasts are radio news, organised by topic; ability to use lesson plans with lots of interesting and varied tasks; tasks can be downloaded to a computer, or done online; ability to choose the type of audio (American, British) and the speed of the audio file.

<http://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org/en/elementary-podcasts>

- Issues are interconnected, topics are relevant and interesting, assignments can be chosen by level of difficulty, they are presented as interactive programmes; opportunity to post feedback, which is covered in subsequent issues.

- On average, one podcast lasts at least 10 minutes; assignments can only be completed online.

<http://www.podcastalley.com/index.php>

- Every month the top 10 most popular podcasts are selected; huge variety of podcasts (radio programmes, shows, series); possibility to add your own podcasts.

- No text of podcasts.

<http://www.allpodcasts.com/podcast search engine>

<http://englishteacherjohn.com/>

- Easy to develop: the author chooses a word, phrase or idiom, explains the meaning and supplements his text with examples; possibility to download podcasts together with the text.

- promotes only lexical skills; podcasts are not factual.
<http://englishpodsong.blogspot.com/>
- availability of songs selected specifically for learning English; when selecting a song, a picture of the artist and other songs are also displayed.
- Podcasts are news that are interesting for an adult audience; availability of video and audio podcasts; large selection of online games, video and audio lessons for those learning English (<http://learningenglish.voanews.com/>).
- Lack of podcast texts, assignments; inability to choose the level of difficulty, lack of search for podcasts by topic.
<http://www.nature.com/podcast/index.html>
- Interesting podcasts on the topic of nature, environment, which are ordered by several radio programmes.
- Lack of text of podcasts; complexity of language.
http://www.npr.org/rss/podcast/podcast_directory.php
- possibility to search podcasts by topic, title, author; availability of a huge number of radio programmes; possibility to listen to radio programmes online; most radio programmes have their own websites.
- lack of access to archives and revision of previous issues; lack of podcast texts, assignments.

The role of English in the modern world is great: every educated person should know English as an international language. There is a great number of information and computer technologies, in particular Internet technologies, which are effective for independent learning of a foreign language. In particular, podcasts contribute to further success in international communication and allow you to learn not only the country whose language is learnt, but also the world as a whole.

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